

1 Exploring Approaches for Large Data in

2 Seismology: User and Data Repository

3 Perspectives

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6 [Abstract](#)

7 New data acquisition techniques are generating data at much finer temporal and spatial
8 resolution compared to traditional seismic experiments. This is a challenge for data centers and
9 users. As the amount of data potentially flowing into data centers increases by one or two
10 orders of magnitude, data management challenges are found throughout all stages of the data
11 flow.

12 The IRIS, RESIF and GEOFON data centers carried out a survey and conducted interviews of
13 users working with very large datasets to understand their needs and expectations. One of the

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14 conclusions is that existing data formats and services are not well suited for users of large
15 datasets. Data centers are exploring storage solutions, data formats, and data delivery options
16 to meet large dataset user needs. New approaches will need to be discussed within the
17 community to establish large dataset standards and best practices, perhaps through
18 participation of stakeholders and users in discussion groups and forums.

19 Introduction

20 New methods of measuring ground motion are significantly reducing the cost of data collection.
21 Two new types of equipment strongly contribute to this cost reduction. The first is nodal data,
22 i.e. data from experiments with a very high number of observation points using low-cost
23 sensors, are now becoming common. As an example, more than 5200 high frequency sensors
24 were deployed over a period of six months in and around Long Beach, California, USA (e.g. Lin et
25 al., 2013). The second is distributed acoustic sensing (DAS) technology, using fiber-optic cables,
26 which is currently being tested and deployed in many locations. As an example, Jousset et al.
27 (2018) deployed a 15-km-long fiber-optic cable layout on Reykjanes Peninsula, SW-Iceland, with
28 a distance of 4 meters between sampling points, to study structural features in the Reykjanes
29 Oblique Rift.

30 Both types of equipment can generate tens to hundreds of terabytes of data at a small fraction
31 of the cost of using traditional seismometers and geophones for equivalent data volumes. As
32 the price of collecting data becomes drastically cheaper, a corresponding and dramatic increase
33 in the volume of data being collected provides a potential scientific bonanza.

34 As dataset sizes increase into the range of tens to hundreds of terabytes however, barriers to
35 storing, transporting, and processing the data begin to appear. The largest collections of openly

36 available seismological data (e.g., as managed by IRIS, RESIF, and GEOFON) measure the volume
37 of their decades-spanning repositories in hundreds of terabytes, yet some new (e.g. DAS)
38 experiments are gathering data volumes well in excess of a hundred terabytes - a significant
39 fraction of the total data volumes presently stored at the seismological data centers. One might
40 suggest that just a small fraction of the data that are collected should be preserved as was
41 suggested decades ago when broadband digital data was first introduced, but tremendous
42 scientific value has been found in the continuous data that was recorded. Storing these data in
43 perpetuity is a significant and daunting challenge, as is delivering datasets exceeding a few tens
44 of terabytes. High-performance/ high-transaction computational resources (HPC/HTC) are
45 increasingly necessary to process these data and these resources are not typically provided by
46 the repositories, nor are they co-located with the repositories.

47 This explosion in data volumes is just beginning and the data centers that have traditionally
48 been the repositories of data for the entire community are not only being asked to host these
49 data for the wider research community but also to accommodate access to the computational
50 resources that are needed to process these data sets. Appropriate data management practices
51 by the data centers must address large data transport, reduced-volume derivative data
52 products, increased access to HPC/HTC, and data formats that are HPC/HTC-friendly.

53 IRIS, RESIF, and GEOFON, all of which are dedicated to providing free and unrestricted access to
54 their data holdings, have attempted to identify the needs of the community and to look for
55 common solutions and best practices for managing very large data sets while maintaining their
56 traditional data services. We begin by presenting the results of soliciting user expectations for
57 large data services through a survey of large data providers and users. Next, we describe the
58 challenges posed by large data from its submission to a data center, to archiving, format

59 considerations, data distribution issues, and finally to the diversity of use cases that data centers
60 provide and will need to provide to serve the research community. The conclusions of this paper
61 provide some possible solutions and strategies for dealing with the challenges of
62 accommodating large data sets. As a community, we must also recognize the environmental
63 impact of storing, processing and transporting large datasets (e.g. carbon footprint due to
64 energy consumption, water usage, pollution from backup generators). The strategy that is
65 eventually implemented by the seismological data centers must take this impact into account
66 and minimize it when at all possible.

67 User Expectations

68 To better serve their users, data centers evaluate the data requests that they receive to improve
69 their existing services and interact with the scientific research and education communities to
70 discover future trends. This provides insight into popular data selection parameters, the data
71 formats requested, and the services that the community uses.

72 User Survey

73 A survey was conducted of selected and self-identified large data users; 37 responses were
74 received. The survey responses indicate that researchers anticipate the following:

- 75 • Large volume use, from 1 to 300+ terabytes, of traditional data (e.g. broadband seismic)
76 and newer data types such as nodal deployments or DAS.
- 77 • Use of both existing data access tools and mechanisms (web services, Python-based
78 clients, miniSEED) and newer data access and processing such as HDF5, Zarr, xarray,
79 especially for larger data sets.

80 The respondents reported the maximum size of the datasets they expect to be working with in
81 the next 3-5 years. We classified them in three different categories of data volume: 21 small (1-
82 9 TB), 11 medium (10-50 TB), and 5 large (50+ TB). We consider the small volume data users
83 relatively well served by current data center capacities, especially as they anticipated using well-
84 established data formats, processing tools and access mechanisms. Medium volume data users,
85 however, are observed to split their data requests into many small requests. What we
86 summarize below are the survey results primarily for the medium and large data users. The
87 results for four important variables are shown in Figure 1.

88 What data type are the raw data (e.g. broadband, nodal, DAS)?

89 The medium data users primarily identified broadband seismic data, nodal data and a bit of
90 DAS, while large data users indicated mostly DAS, with some nodal and broadband seismic.

91 From which data centers do you expect to request large data volumes?

92 Users from all categories indicated using a wide variety of data centers, which we interpret to
93 indicate they will access data from wherever they can get it, with no particular preference.

94 In which data format(s) would you prefer to work with large data (miniSEED, SAC, PH5, ASDF,
95 HDF5, etc.)?

96 Both medium and large data users anticipated a use of a variety of data formats, but primarily
97 miniSEED, HDF5 (PH5 and ASDF), with a few cases of Zarr (see Data and Resources). However,
98 for users planning to work with 20+ TB, the option of miniSEED reduces considerably in
99 comparison to HDF5-based formats or other less standard formats.

100 Would you process the data with standard codes? With your own code? Using third party
101 frameworks and libraries (e.g. ObsPy)?

102 Users from all categories indicated the most common codes they expect to use would mostly be
103 their own code, supported by ObsPy (Beyreuther et al., 2010) or MATLAB.

104 Which programming language(s) do you, or would you expect to, use for data processing and
105 analysis?

106 Python is the most indicated programming language of choice, followed by MATLAB, C/C++,
107 Fortran and Julia.

108 Where would you prefer the data to be delivered: your own compute infrastructure, a cloud
109 system, an HPC center?

110 Many medium and large users indicated that they would like to transfer data to their own
111 computer infrastructure or their institutional infrastructure. Many also indicated a preference to
112 deliver data to an HPC center one of whom anticipated relying on commercial cloud providers.

113 Would you be willing to pay for the data processing resources (e.g. compute) if the data are
114 available within a commercial cloud or other environment that is not free to use?

115 Many users are willing to pay (some dependent on grant allowance) for processing. However, as
116 in previous questions, among users working with 20+ TB there seems to be a clear trend in favor
117 of paying. Some pointed out that it should be an option to transfer the data to a location where
118 they would not be required to pay for processing.

119 Please briefly summarize your current large data processing workflow, trouble points
120 identified/foreseen, and how it can be improved.

121 Most users indicated that they use largely ad hoc data processing workflows, with a few
122 identifying the need for parallel processing and processing-ready data access such as from HDF5
123 containers. The common challenge for many is efficient access to large volume data, either due
124 to access interface issues or limited transfer capability.

125 Which software would you use to access/download large data volumes (libraries, applications,
126 etc.)?

127 Users of all scales report they expect to use the existing tools and mechanisms of web services,
128 ObsPy, or directly in their own codes (in Python or Julia). A few report their anticipated use of
129 larger platforms such as Pangeo, direct access to object storage (e.g. S3), specialised libraries
130 (e.g. xarray), and advanced data containers such as Zarr.

131 Other comments

132 When asked for other comments or their vision for large seismic data processing in the future,
133 users identified the need to develop access and transfer mechanisms for large volumes of data.
134 Additionally, they noted the need for advanced data formats appropriate for large data, the
135 desire for derived (reduced volume) data products for easier use, their preference for compute
136 resources in the same system as the data (to avoid transfer), and cloud ready seismic processing
137 software. Finally, the users expressed their desire for continued collaboration between
138 international seismological data centers so that researchers can discover and access large
139 volumes of data wherever it is available.

140 [Diversity of Data Requests](#)

141 From the survey and from the experience of the IRIS, GEOFON, and RESIF data centers, requests
142 for medium and large data sets span a range of time and spatial scales. On one end of the
143 spectrum are studies that require hours/days of high sample-rate data collected from densely
144 spaced sensors, and at the other end of the spectrum are studies that require decades of broad-
145 band data from stations distributed around the globe.

146 The survey clearly demonstrates that the DAS experiments represent the largest volume
147 datasets; however, both the survey and data center experience show that Medium and Large

148 data volumes from traditional seismic stations are increasingly in demand. Two typical uses of
149 such Medium and Large datasets include studies based on cross correlation techniques and
150 studies using machine learning methods (ML). In such cases, large datasets are created from
151 years-long time series from a large number of individual seismic stations either at global,
152 regional or local scales and the data needed for a comprehensive study may even be distributed
153 across several data centers on different continents. In contrast, requests for node data or other
154 experimental data with high frequency sampling are often based on data from a single data
155 center. Users may want access to the entire dataset or to a specific time or spatial slice. DAS
156 datasets can be much larger than anything that traditional data centers supporting the scientific
157 research and education communities have experience in managing. Like nodal data, researchers
158 may want access to the entire dataset or to subsets of the full dataset; they may also want to
159 process those data without transporting them or need to have them delivered to an HPC center
160 rather than to their home institutions. Because of these processing needs, data centers should
161 be aware of the data formats that are efficient for high-performance computation and be able
162 to deliver data in some of those formats.

163 The management and organization of data and user services need to be flexible enough to
164 handle not only the requests for medium and large datasets, but also for the diversity of
165 standard data requests for a small number of seismic stations and short time periods (small
166 datasets). Data centers need to encourage and enhance services associated with data requests
167 using criteria such as station location, instrument type, sampling rate, data quality, data
168 repository location, or more advanced parameters associated with earthquake parameters,
169 propagation path, local geology at the seismic station, etc. MUSTANG (Casey et al., 2018) and

170 WFCatalog (Trani et al, 2017) are some examples of services that allow users to pre-select data
171 based on quality metrics.

172 The Challenges of Large Data

173 The seismological community has a long tradition of collaborative work between data centers
174 and researchers. In Europe data centers collaborate through Observatories & Research Facilities
175 for European Seismology (ORFEUS), while global collaboration in the seismological community is
176 through the International Federation of Digital Seismograph Networks (FDSN). One of the most
177 important achievements for the discipline is the establishment of well-defined standards under
178 the coordination of the FDSN. These include not only the data formats, but also detailed
179 specifications for providing data/metadata services and how Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)
180 should be used to identify seismic networks. Standards approved by the global community
181 within the FDSN allow seismological data centers to support the Findable, Accessible,
182 Interoperable, and Repeatable (FAIR) data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016). This global
183 collaboration has contributed to a greater sharing of data among all seismologists and is a
184 model for other disciplines.

185 Specifications regarding formats and services were designed in a totally different landscape of
186 operational limitations and data usage compared to what the community will face from now on.
187 As soon as the amount of data increases one or two orders of magnitude, technical problems
188 are expected. From the data center perspective, large data management challenges are found in
189 the following stages of the data flow: (a) data submission, (b) data archival, (c) creation of
190 proper metadata, (d) data distribution, and (e) data usage (Figure 2).

191 [Data Submission](#)

192 In the cases of Large-N or DAS experiments the volume of data submitted to a data center could
193 be hundreds of terabytes. Here, it is important to make a distinction between temporary and
194 permanent experiments. For temporary experiments, data are usually acquired in the field and
195 either transmitted or physically transported to the data center. Field data storage devices can
196 be mounted on the data center's network and the data ingested into the system. In the case of
197 permanent deployments, data are usually transmitted to the data center in real-time by means
198 of protocols like SeedLink. However, for high volume data such as from DAS experiments, real-
199 time transmission of the full-resolution data may not be practical. One option for DAS
200 installations is to pre-process the data at the station to reduce the data volume before
201 transmitting them to a data center. Raw data would still be available for later delivery to a data
202 center or, should no data center be capable of handling the volume, a suitable archive found by
203 the operator of the DAS installation.

204 [Data Archive Planning](#)

205 Designing an efficient data management system for seismological data requires consideration of
206 several aspects: the storage hardware, the data format(s), and the way data will be accessed.
207 These three factors are connected; storage system performance varies depending on user
208 access requirements, which are supported by the format of the data. Requests that require
209 gathering small snippets of data from many files require higher performance storage systems
210 than requests for data in a single file.
211 The internal data management of seismological data centers is not specified by FDSN; data
212 centers are free to manage their data as they see fit and store the data they have in their

213 repositories and archives in whatever format suits their use cases. The data provisioning system,
214 fdsnws-dataselect (see Data and Resources), must deliver data in the miniSEED format, but the
215 data centers are free to use different data formats to archive data and perform the conversion
216 on-the-fly before sending them to users.

217 To date, the miniSEED format has been very popular as a storage format among data centers
218 because it is highly compatible with the software ecosystem in the community. The main
219 advantages are that there is no need to convert on-the-fly when sending most data to users and
220 that datasets can be formed by a concatenation of miniSEED records that can be streamed as
221 they are retrieved from the storage media. The ability to stream data directly avoids the need to
222 stage the dataset on the server side before sending it. The disadvantage is that miniSEED has no
223 inherent indexing capability; users typically use the file system as a means to organize and
224 locate data, which may require a huge number of files for medium and large datasets.

225 For medium and large datasets, the HDF5 format is popular among users of HPC. Two popular
226 HDF5-based formats in our community are PH5 (Hess et al., 2018) and ASDF (Krischer et al.,
227 2016). Initial experimentation has indicated that a reduction in storage space is possible using
228 PH5, likely due to the longer data segments being compressed. A redesign of the PH5 format to
229 make it more versatile is expected to be completed in 2021. The new format is expected to be
230 usable not only for nodal data, but also for DAS, Magnetotelluric, geodetic, and other data
231 types. A generic HDF5-based solution could have some advantages not only for data centers but
232 also for users needing to process their large datasets in an HPC-friendly format. The main
233 disadvantage for data centers is that HDF5 formatted data cannot currently be streamed on the
234 fly as they are read by the data provisioning systems (see Data Distribution). However, there is a

235 rich ecosystem of interesting open source tools supporting HDF5 such as the THREDDS Data
236 Server (Unidata, 2020) or HSDS distribution services (see Data and Resources).

237 Other file formats were mentioned in the user’s survey, but data center experience with these
238 formats is limited. The desirable features of formats like Zarr, which allow dynamic data
239 chunking, haven’t been thoroughly tested in the community. In Table 1 we summarize some of
240 the file formats and their characteristics. The different data format features must be explored to
241 optimize the trade-offs between efficient data compression, fast data extraction, and streaming.
242 Increases of volume also imply new strategies for choice of physical storage. If data centers are
243 expected to increase their archive sizes by at least one order of magnitude (or even more), it
244 might not be feasible to keep all of the data online (Figure 3). Offline storage should probably be
245 considered inside the data center or provided by external services. This will raise the storage
246 capacity but data would have to be staged on demand, and with limited size and retention time.
247 Considering the costs, one should consider that the long-term archival of data implies not only
248 the cost of the storage units, but also the backup strategy, the renewal of the hardware (e.g.
249 hard drives) every 5-7 years, and the regular procedures to ensure that data are still readable.

250 One way to optimize data storage is to utilize tiered storage strategies; keep data that are rarely
251 accessed in slower, cheaper systems and data that are requested frequently on systems that
252 provide rapid access. Managing how data are tiered could potentially be dynamic, based on past
253 access patterns. However, these patterns are not easily discerned.

254 Some data centers have already tested commercial cloud services as a storage system to
255 evaluate the feasibility of migrating their archives to the cloud. Despite the technical advantages
256 of this approach, there are financial drawbacks that deserve serious consideration, particularly
257 for large data centers that hold petabytes of data in their repositories, that require substantial

258 compute resources to manage their data, and that deliver petabytes of data each year to their
259 users.

260 An important consideration regarding choice of storage system is whether the data will be
261 accessed directly for processing in addition to supporting general extraction systems. Direct
262 data access adds a new dimension to the usage patterns and presents a challenge for managing
263 access permissions, request rates, response times, etc. Direct data access for processing should
264 not be allowed to deteriorate services associated with standard data requests.

265 [Data Description](#)

266 There exist comprehensive metadata standards in seismology that are well suited for large
267 nodal data sets or other classical seismic data sets. However, newer, emerging data types such
268 as DAS are not as well handled by these standards where the concepts of a network, station,
269 location and a channel are different and the fundamental instrument responses are new.
270 Therefore, one of the most difficult tasks for data centers attempting to identify and implement
271 standard services is to standardize DAS metadata through the definition of new metadata
272 schemas. StationXML, the international standard for seismic metadata, is not a good fit with the
273 technical features of DAS interrogators and the generated datasets. There is a need to tackle
274 this in a smart way in order to make these data available and interoperable with all popular
275 tools used within the community, which expect typical seismic waveforms with some minimum
276 set of requirements on their metadata, and the possibility of mixing different data types.
277 A non-technical (and still pending) issue is how to name DAS data sampling points. If the first
278 approach to standardize and distribute DAS experiment data is to generate derived products as
279 suggested by many users, there are some details to be considered. Should DAS experiments be
280 registered by the FDSN in order to get a formal network code? If this is not the case, how could

281 a user identify or select the required sampling points? To have a network code registered would
282 allow the dataset to be uniquely distinguished from other experiments. This would also allow
283 one to formally assign a DOI and the proper citation to the experiment, as agreed and expected
284 in the community.

285 At levels finer than the network, should each sampling point be considered a station, a location
286 or a channel? If we consider that each fiber could have thousands of sampling points with a
287 spatial separation as small as of 2 to 4 meters and a length of tens of kilometers, a station
288 designation seems to be the best fit. As stations have a unique position, we cannot consider
289 such a deployment to be a single-station-multiple-channels configuration. We note that the ISC
290 applies a 1-km station rule for the International Registry of Stations that is generally followed by
291 the community. Quoting ISC: "Because of the need for accurate station positions for hypocenter
292 location programs, a new international code is assigned if a station is moved more than one (1)
293 kilometer from the previous location". Although having locations codes more than a kilometer
294 away from the station does not technically violate the rule about stations that move, we believe
295 that it would be extremely confusing to have channels with a location up to 50 kilometers away
296 from their associated station. We also note that some large array deployments (like the
297 Norwegian Seismic Array Network, see Data and Resources) identify each array element with
298 different station names.

299 A reasonable approach would be to define a station for each sampling point, similar to the
300 situation in nodal experiments where each node is typically assigned a station code. These
301 naming conventions will be fundamental for interoperability between data centers, as well as a
302 homogeneous definition of the subsets independent of who is archiving the data.

303 As described above, simple information such as latitude, longitude and orientation are already a
304 challenge, whose solution is not trivial and could potentially make a difference in the results if
305 data should be automatically processed. It seems unavoidable to perform some post-processing
306 of the data to calculate the exact location of each sampling point. This should be based on the
307 GPS information from the interrogator and the detection of an active source (e.g. “tap test”)
308 during the deployment phase. Standard and generic codes, benchmarks and guidelines provided
309 to/by the community would be desirable, and information about the postprocessing needs to
310 integrate the metadata.

311 Some of these topics are being discussed within community user groups, like the Distributed
312 Acoustic Sensing Research Coordination Network (DAS RCN, see Data and Resources) and
313 hopefully some proposals to standardize the description of DAS experiments will emerge. The
314 needs and related challenges from the irruption of new technologies, like DAS interrogators,
315 could be the triggering factor to discuss the long-term evolution of our current standards (e.g.
316 StationXML) and to potentially explore more generic formats like SensorML, which is widely
317 used in Geophysics and generic enough to encompass all that StationXML can express.

318 [Data Distribution](#)

319 Currently, the FDSN-standard suite of web services (fdsnws-station and fdsnws-dataselect) are
320 used by many researchers to discover and download data. From April to September 2020, 90%
321 of the fdsnws-dataselect requests received delivered less than 5 MB of data (Figure 4). The
322 miniSEED format along with the fdsnws-dataselect webservice are well designed for this
323 purpose. However, users may make many small requests to optimize their data retrieval success
324 and assemble the complete dataset that they desire on their computers. The size of the
325 datasets needed by the community is probably larger than is observed in Figure 4. It is still

326 unclear what the download pattern for Large-N or DAS data would be, but downloads of entire
327 datasets are expected.

328 The distribution of large data sets (50+ TB) is challenging due to bandwidth constraints. As
329 mentioned previously, one of the main results of the survey we conducted was that the full
330 resolution data is not needed for most studies, particularly for DAS. Instead, a set of products
331 derived from the original data would satisfy most users. The derived data products are often a
332 significantly reduced volume making them more feasible for archiving and distribution by
333 existing data centers and systems. While the derivative products are useful in reducing the
334 burden of transferring bulky data, the need to transfer large volumes is not eliminated for all
335 users.

336 Another significant challenge is the lack of available services to handle the transmission of large
337 volumes. The current data transfer standard in global broadband seismology (fdsnws-
338 dataselect), defines a synchronous web service interface that accepts arbitrary data selections
339 and is expected to begin returning data with little or no delay. It has become a highly successful
340 mechanism, but although allowed, requesting large data volumes with this service has the risk
341 of causing connection timeouts. It is difficult to efficiently resume transfers following broken
342 connections, which are increasingly likely with very large volumes. Also, maintaining acceptable
343 performance can require significant software and system engineering by the data centers.

344 One tool, IRIS's ROVER (see Data and Resources), has overcome the issue of dropped
345 connections by using a smart client to manage the synchronous data transfer in miniSEED, and
346 constructing the final dataset on the client side. This approach requires a relatively complex
347 client, but is a robust and efficient method of requesting large datasets.

348 Future distribution capabilities worth exploration are the use of GridFTP (Allcock et al., 2005), or
349 rsync (see Data and Resources) for efficient bulk file transfer. But these methods can only be
350 used with existing files and not arbitrary data selections. Another possibility is the extension of
351 web service interfaces like fdsnws-dataselect to allow asynchronous, or batch, data transfer to a
352 site (e.g. HPC center) identified by the requestor. In other cases and depending on the archive
353 format, some middleware solutions such as THREDDS Data Server (Unidata, 2020) or HSDS (see
354 Data and Resources) could potentially be useful solutions for sub-selecting and transforming
355 large data volumes.

356 [Using the Data](#)

357 Considering the classical approach of data usage by seismologists, some important
358 requirements have been identified in the previous sections, in particular the need for standard
359 data and metadata formats, and correct and complete metadata. Presently, only miniSEED is an
360 FDSN standard within the community, but this format is inefficient and cumbersome for
361 processing large datasets. Non-FDSN standard formats (e.g. HDF5 based) are presently being
362 used by researchers working with medium and large datasets (20+TB) and they would like to get
363 data in this format from the data center provisioning systems. The definition of an additional
364 FDSN standard aimed at large datasets would spur the development of community processing
365 tools, and would greatly further the cooperation and sharing of resources between data
366 centers.

367 The user's need to process data in a remote environment (e.g. cloud computing, containers),
368 means that other factors should also be considered by data centers. For instance, even if a data
369 center can provide a container or Jupyter notebook (see Data and Resources) with direct
370 processing of the data, solutions need to be developed to limit restricted dataset access to

371 authorized users. This is not a minor issue, as most of these large datasets go under an embargo
372 period of some years before being opened to the public. This means that depending on the
373 user, only part of the archive should be accessible to any given user from the computing
374 interfaces. A similar issue is related to the data organization (format and structure). The data
375 center can expose (or let the user access) what exists in the storage system so the user will in
376 principle be able to use only the storage format. It will be difficult (and in some cases
377 impossible) to stage a new dataset in another format to be accessed by the user. Therefore, the
378 data format and organization needs to be known by the user. As each data center is free to
379 organize the data in whatever way is optimal to them, data processing software cannot easily be
380 used across different data center computational facilities.

381 The transparent federation of data is probably the biggest challenge for data centers because it
382 includes not only all the improvements and developments mentioned in this article, but also the
383 edge case in which multiple large datasets are requested from different data centers. In such a
384 case, even running the code on top of the data is not a solution. That would only save the
385 transfer from that data center, but there is still the problem of requesting all the other data.
386 Some public initiatives exist in the United States and Europe to propose solutions to the
387 problem of federated data (e.g. XSEDE/Jetstream and the European Open Science Cloud).
388 However, there are still no solutions available that cover all the aspects mentioned above.

389 Conclusions

390 Despite present initiatives trying to tackle the problem of big seismological datasets and how
391 they can be archived, delivered, and processed, data centers are facing a situation similar to
392 that from the mid-80's. Namely, the amount of data generated was much bigger than the data

393 centers could safely and sustainably archive. At that moment, the temporary solution was to
394 keep only time windows of interest (e.g. waveforms related to an event) and discard the rest of
395 the data after some time. What has been learned from this experience is that discarding data is
396 not the best option to consider, as illustrated by present day research in data mining, new types
397 of seismic signals, and imaging techniques using seismic noise.

398 With the present increase of data volumes come additional problems associated with the
399 internal organization of data within the data centers and meeting the need for data formats that
400 are well adapted for storing and slicing big datasets. Along with these problems, there is a need
401 for adapting present data request tools or developing new ones.

402 At present, the IRIS, GEOFON and RESIF data centers recognize that it is not possible for them to
403 permanently archive very large datasets such as DAS due to prohibitive costs of long-term
404 archiving. Safe storage (involving multiple copies) of such large datasets available online is
405 presently not possible either. Therefore, the seismological data centers should explore a
406 strategy for delivering datasets through automatic asynchronous services to designated
407 destinations such as computing facilities where data pre-processing or processing could occur.
408 For very large datasets, a common strategy is needed for storing only standard data products
409 such as spatially and/or temporally down-sampled data, and/or small windows of highly
410 sampled data.

411 Ideally, in the long term, international standards and products should be developed within the
412 framework of the FDSN. As a preparatory phase, we suggest to undertake the following actions:

- 413 • Encourage a wide and continuous international collaboration on DAS data. This would
414 include dedicated workshops and special sessions in conferences involving data centers
415 and scientific users who could define a limited set of standard products for DAS data.

416 One natural forum would be a strong international presence in the Distributed Acoustic
417 Sensing Research Coordination Network (DAS RCN), which involves both scientific users
418 and data center operators/managers.

- 419 • Extend the present discussion between our three data centers to other interested data
420 centers. One option is to set up dedicated technical workshops on very focused subjects,
421 including solutions to keep the raw data safely for future use. Our community should in
422 these workshops interact with data centers from other disciplines to understand
423 similarities and differences of use cases and technical constraints, to benefit from past
424 experience over a broad range of scientific areas, and to explore possible common
425 technical solutions.

426 This preparatory work hopefully will lead to new community standards and user services that
427 are well adapted to large datasets.

428 Data and Resources

429 The SEED Manual can be downloaded from http://www.fdsn.org/pdf/SEEDManual_V2.4.pdf .

430 Information about HSDS can be read from <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/highly-scalable->

431 <data-service-hsds/> . Documentation of Zarr can be found at <https://zarr.readthedocs.io/> .

432 Information about the DAS Research Coordination Network (DAS RCN) can be found at

433 https://www.iris.edu/hq/initiatives/das_rcn . Specifications of the FDSN web services can be

434 found at <http://fdsn.org/webservices/FDSN-WS-Specifications-1.2.pdf> . Information on the

435 Norwegian Seismic Array Network (NO) can be found at

436 <http://www.fdsn.org/networks/detail/NO/> . Details of the International Registry of

437 Seismographic Stations can be read from <http://www.isc.ac.uk/registries/registration/> .

438 Documentation of ROVER can be found at <https://iris-edu.github.io/rover/> . Rsync information
439 available at <https://rsync.samba.org/> . Information about Jupyter Notebooks is available at
440 <https://jupyter.org/> . Plots were made using Matplotlib (Hunter, 2007).

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510

511 Table 1: Summary of data formats mentioned in the survey and some of their relevant
 512 advantages and disadvantages.

Format	Comments regarding use in large data management
miniSEED SEED (2012)	miniSEED is an international seismological standard for data exchange that is also commonly used for archiving. It was designed for independent, single time series, usually very small chunk sizes, and not for processing.
PH5 (Hess et al., 2018)	PH5 is an HDF5 based format. A rich toolbox has been provided by PASSCAL but data subsetting is not possible without high-level translation and streaming the base format is not supported.
ASDF (Krischer et al., 2018)	ASDF is an HDF5 based format. Data subsetting is not possible without high-level translation and streaming the base format is not supported.
Zarr ZARR (2020)	Zarr is a format and a python library to manage numerical arrays. Data subsetting is allowed and it is a good design for HPC. Zarr has not been used much in the geophysical community and is only for python.
ADIOS2 (Godoy et al., 2020)	ADIOS2 is a framework for data IO management; it is not broadly known or used in seismology.

513

514

515 Figure Captions

516

517 Figure 1: Different aspects of users' data workflows by size of datasets to be requested. Counts
518 at the base of bars are the number of respondents. Smaller datasets tend to be requested in
519 miniSEED format, but HDF5-based formats are preferred for larger datasets. Requests to get
520 nodal experiment data will generate medium size datasets, while users plan to get very large
521 datasets from DAS experiments. Python is the preferred programming independent of the
522 dataset size. Small datasets are expected to be staged in the user infrastructure, while larger
523 datasets in some HPC facility. Only a few users mentioned their will to stage data in a cloud
524 service.

525

526 Figure 2: Schematic view of the different parts of the data flow in a seismological data center.
527 The inputs are (a) data and (c) data description (metadata), submitted by the producer. Both
528 inputs are managed in separate workflows to be hosted in (b) data archive and (c') metadata
529 database. Data distribution services (d) need access to both repositories in order to handle the
530 (e) final user's requests. Challenges regarding large data in a, b, c, d and e are described in this
531 paper.

532

533 Figure 3: Evolution of the data archived yearly at each data center (green, yellow, and blue
534 curves). The error bars on the right show the expected size range of a single dataset for a Large-
535 N (blue) and a DAS (red) experiment. It can be seen that a single large dataset could be
536 equivalent in size to a whole year of the typical datasets currently being archived.

537

538 Figure 4: Percentage of requests per request size and data center. Statistics have been
539 calculated from April 2020 to September 2020. 90% of the requests are less than 5 MB. Note
540 however that some users request intermediate size volumes through thousands of small data
541 requests. The dataset sizes needed by users could be much larger than what is shown here.
542

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Archival rate per year

Figure 4

Percentage of requests by size

